

22IEM06 S-CALe Up

D6

Validation of new photodiodes with improved performance and UV – stability from 200 nm to 400 nm suitable as spectral responsivity standards

Organisation name of the lead participant for the deliverable:

SINTEF

Due date of the deliverable: May 2026

Actual submission date of the deliverable: May 2026

Confidentiality Status: PU - Public, fully open (remember to deposit public deliverables in a trusted repository)

Deliverable Cover Sheet

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or EURAMET. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

The project has received funding from the European Partnership on Metrology, co-financed from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and by the Participating States.

European Partnership Co-funded by the European Union

METROLOGY PARTNERSHIP

TABLE OF CONTENTS

22IEM06 S-CALe Up	1
SINTEF	1
1 Summary	3
2 Attachment – Paper I: Improving UV Stability of SiO ₂ /SiN _x -Passivated Silicon Photodiodes Through Shallow Junction Implantation and Oxide Regrowth.....	4

1 Summary

This deliverable reports the validation work carried out on silicon photodiodes developed for improved UV stability and suitability as spectral responsivity standards in the 200–400 nm wavelength range. The deliverable was fully achieved.

The work has been focused on understanding the degradation mechanisms of $\text{SiO}_2/\text{SiN}_x$ -passivated induced-junction photodiodes under UV exposure, with particular emphasis on 222 nm, and on evaluating process modifications to improve device stability. Electrical characterization of MIS capacitors and symmetrically passivated wafers early in the project showed that UV exposure leads to a reduction in effective dielectric charge and passivation quality, which was identified as an important cause of degradation in induced-junction devices. Induced-junction photodiodes were found to exhibit rapid photocurrent loss under 222 nm exposure and, in some cases, eventual collapse.

To improve UV stability, shallow implanted junctions based on As and Sb were developed and validated. After an initial screening of 18 different processes, in which the resulting sheet resistance, dopant profile and UV response was evaluated, a photodiode batch comprising 44 wafers with 11 different process variations was fabricated and tested.

Devices with shallow As or Sb implants showed substantially improved stability compared with induced-junction photodiodes, maintaining significantly higher normalized photocurrent under prolonged 222 nm exposure.

A further improvement was achieved by removing the retained implantation screen oxide and replacing it with regrown thermal oxide prior to dielectric deposition. Photodiodes fabricated with regrown oxide showed the best stability, with nearly unchanged photocurrent up to approximately 500 J/cm^2 at 222 nm.

The results demonstrate that improved UV stability can be achieved by reducing device dependence on dielectric-induced inversion and by improving the post-implantation oxide/interface quality. These findings support the development of silicon photodiodes with enhanced suitability for use as stable spectral responsivity standards in the UV range.

The attached manuscript submitted to *Sensors* documents the fabrication, characterization, UV exposure experiments, and interpretation of the results in detail.

2 Attachment – Paper I: Improving UV Stability of SiO₂/SiN_x-Passivated Silicon Photodiodes Through Shallow Junction Implantation and Oxide Regrowth

Improving UV Stability of SiO₂/SiN_x-Passivated Silicon Photodiodes Through Shallow Junction Implantation and Oxide Regrowth

Michael N. Getz^{1*}, Ozhan Koybasi¹, Fredrik Edhborg², Ørnulf Nordseth³, Steven Hesse⁴, Tobias Pohl⁴, Marco Povoli¹, Stefan Källberg², Lutz Werner⁴, Erkki Ikonen⁵, Jarle Gran⁶

¹ SINTEF Digital, Smart Sensors and Microsystems, 0314 Oslo, Norway
² RISE Research Institutes of Sweden AB, Borås, Sweden
³ Dep. of Solar Energy Materials and Technologies, Institute for Energy Technology, 2027 Kjeller, Norway
⁴ Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt, 10587 Berlin, Germany
⁵ Aalto University and VTT MIKES, 02150 Espoo, Finland
⁶ Justervesenet, 2027 Kjeller, Norway
* Correspondence: michael.getz@sintef.no

Abstract

Induced-junction silicon photodiodes based on SiO₂/SiN_x surface passivation are attractive for high-accuracy radiometry, but their use in the deep-ultraviolet is limited by UV-induced degradation of the dielectric stack. In this work, we investigate the degradation of SiO₂/SiN_x-passivated p-type silicon photodiodes under UV exposure and evaluate strategies for improving stability through shallow implanted junctions and oxide processing. Capacitance–voltage measurements on MIS capacitors and lifetime measurements on symmetrically passivated wafers show that UV exposure causes a rapid reduction in effective dielectric charge and carrier lifetime, followed by saturation at higher dose. For exposure at 222 and 279 nm, the effective charge saturates at ca. 3×10¹¹ cm⁻², whereas exposure at 300 nm saturates at a higher level of ca. 7×10¹¹ cm⁻², indicating that degradation is governed by filling of a finite population of electrically active trap states. Induced-junction photodiodes exhibit rapid photocurrent loss at 222 nm and, in some cases, eventual collapse. In contrast, photodiodes with shallow implanted As or Sb junctions show an initial reduction followed by stabilization at around 80–85% of the initial value up to the highest tested dose of 200 J/cm². Further improvement is achieved by stripping and regrowing the screen oxide, yielding nearly unchanged photocurrent after prolonged 222 nm exposure up to ca. 500 J/cm². These results show that UV stability can be substantially improved by reducing device dependence on dielectric-induced inversion and by improving interfacial oxide quality.

Keywords: Induced-junction photodiodes, Ultraviolet photodiodes, Silicon photodiodes, SiO₂/SiN_x passivation, Shallow ion implantation, UV stability

Academic Editor: Firstname Last-name

Received: date

Revised: date

Accepted: date

Published: date

Citation: To be added by editorial staff during production.

Copyright: © 2025 by the authors. Submitted for possible open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. Introduction

Induced junction photodiodes based on dielectric surface passivation have emerged as promising candidates for high-accuracy optical radiometry and predictable quantum-efficient detectors [1], [2], [3], [4]. By exploiting fixed positive charge in dielectric stacks

such as SiO₂/SiN_x to create a near-surface inversion layer in p-type silicon, these devices enable efficient carrier collection without a conventional diffused junction [3], [5], [6]. This principle forms the basis of Predictable Quantum Efficient Detectors (PQEDs), which can achieve near-unity internal quantum efficiency (IQE) and extremely low internal quantum deficiency (IQD), making them attractive for primary optical power standards [3], [5].

We previously demonstrated SiO₂/SiN_x-induced junction photodiodes with record-high quantum efficiency in the 400 nm to 700 nm range, achieving IQD below 10⁻⁵ across the visible spectrum [3]. These results confirmed the suitability of dielectric-induced junctions for high-precision radiometry in the visible. However, extending operation into the ultraviolet (UV) region introduces additional challenges, as carrier generation shifts closer to the surface and device performance becomes increasingly sensitive to dielectric stability and interface quality.

UV irradiation is known to modify dielectric materials through mechanisms such as charge trapping, bond breaking, and defect generation [7], [8], [9], [10]. In PECVD SiN_x, UV exposure can alter fixed charge density and increase interface-state density, thereby degrading surface passivation and modifying the induced electric field [9], [10], [11]. We have previously shown that adding a thin interfacial thermal SiO₂ layer significantly lowers IQD despite the lower positive fixed charge of SiO₂ compared with SiN_x [3]. This improvement arises from the superior interface quality of thermal SiO₂, which substantially reduces interface defect density [12], [13], [14], [15]. The SiN_x layer remains desirable, not only because of its high positive fixed charge [16], but because it serves as a hydrogen reservoir that can passivate dangling bonds at the Si/SiO₂ interface [3], [13]. In addition, its refractive index makes it useful as an antireflective coating. At the same time, SiO₂ itself can exhibit UV-induced charge modification, particularly at shorter wavelengths [7], [8], and the combined SiO₂/SiN_x stack has been shown to exhibit wavelength- and dose-dependent degradation under UV [10], [11]. However, for creating induced junctions on p-type silicon, there are currently no suitable UV-transparent alternatives to thermal SiO₂ or SiN_x, making the development of UV-stable passivation schemes important for applications in which p-type silicon is desired.

For induced junction photodiodes fabricated on p-type silicon, the functionality of the device critically depends on maintaining sufficient positive fixed charge in the dielectric to sustain inversion at the surface. We have previously observed a collapse of photocurrent during UV exposure below 300 nm [11], indicating that the dielectric charge state becomes a limiting factor in the deep-UV.

In the present work, we investigate the evolution of dielectric charge and passivation quality under UV exposure to better understand the degradation of SiO₂/SiN_x-induced junction photodiodes. We further examine whether shallow external implantation can improve stability at 222 nm by reducing device dependence on dielectric-induced inversion. Finally, we investigate the effect of stripping and regrowing the screen oxide after implantation, rather than thinning the screen oxide to the desired thickness to assess the role of oxide quality in UV degradation.

The results provide insight into the physical mechanisms governing UV-induced modification of dielectric stacks and clarify the role of junction engineering and oxide processing in extending the operational wavelength range of high-accuracy silicon photodiodes toward the deep-UV region.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Device Fabrication

Three different structure categories were investigated in this study: (i) symmetrically passivated implanted and unimplanted silicon wafers for lifetime measurements, (ii) MIS

capacitors for dielectric characterization, and (iii) photodiodes with either induced or shallow implanted junctions.

2.1.1 Dielectric Stack

Dielectric stacks were prepared using 500 μm float-zone P-type (boron) Si(100) wafers from GlobalWafers with resistivity of 5–12 $\text{k}\Omega\cdot\text{cm}$.

All wafers were subjected to a HF dip, SC1 ($\text{NH}_4\text{OH}/\text{H}_2\text{O}_2/\text{H}_2\text{O}$), and SC2 ($\text{HCl}/\text{H}_2\text{O}_2/\text{H}_2\text{O}$) treatments followed by DI water rinsing and spin drying.

Preparation of the basic induced junction stack consisted of ca. 6.5 nm thermal SiO_2 grown at 1000 $^\circ\text{C}$ in a horizontal tube furnace, followed by ca. 65 nm PECVD SiN_x using a $\text{SiH}_4:\text{NH}_3$ flow ratio of 1:3. The development of this stack has been described previously in [3].

For shallow junction formation, selected wafers were implanted with As or Sb at Ion Beam Services (France) and furnace-annealed prior to dielectric stack formation. Implant and annealing parameters were selected based on profile simulations. A 30 nm thermal screen oxide was grown on these wafers prior to implantation. After annealing, the screen oxide on the symmetrically implanted test wafers was trimmed down to ca. 4 nm in a SC1 bath. The target thickness was 6 nm, but the etch was difficult to control due to the altered etch behaviour of the implanted oxide and changes in bath activity over time. 65 nm SiN_x was then deposited using the same PECVD process. For photodiode production the screen oxide was instead trimmed down to ca. 15 nm prior to deposition of 26 nm PECVD SiN_x . A summary of implantation and annealing conditions is provided in Table S1.

2.1.2 MIS capacitors

Wafers used for impedance measurements were heavily implanted with boron on the backside to form a low-resistance ohmic contact and were passivated only on the front side. Aluminium (150 nm) was deposited on both sides by thermal evaporation. Circular front-side electrodes (diameter: 1, 2 and 3 mm) were defined by shadow mask.

2.1.3 Photodiodes

Photodiodes of active areas of 11 mm \times 11 mm, and 11 mm \times 22 mm were included in the wafer layout. A diagram of the layout is presented in Figure 1. The design included an n^+ ring for contacting the active area, a p-stop ring for isolation, an n^+ guard ring to suppress edge leakage, and a p^+ ring at the periphery for top-side contact to the substrate.

For the photodiode fabrication, the same wafer types were included as was used for preparing the dielectric stacks. In addition, a few diodes were prepared on 500 μm FZ, P-type Si (111) wafers with $> 5 \text{ k}\Omega\cdot\text{cm}$ from Global Net Corp.

A thick thermal SiO_2 layer was first grown to serve as field oxide during processing. The wafers were processed using six photomask layers that were used to define the areas of p^+ implantation, n^+ implantation, shallow As/Sb doping, active area dielectric passivation, contact holes through SiO_2 , and metallization. The p^+ and n^+ electrodes were made with boron and phosphorus implantation, respectively. Multiple implantation and dielectric stack variations were evaluated for the active area. A complete list of all tested variations is presented in Table S2. The wafers were metallized with 1.2 μm Al on both sides.

2.2 Methodology

Oxide and nitride thicknesses were determined by spectroscopic ellipsometry in the 371 nm to 1000 nm range using standard optical models for thermal SiO_2 and SiN_x .

Figure 1: Cross-sectional schematic of the photodiode structure used in this work, showing the induced-junction (inversion-layer) active area and the biasing of the contact ring and guard ring. The n^+ regions (phosphorus implant) provide electrical contact to the induced junction and guard ring, while p^+ regions (boron implant) form the p-stop and substrate contacts. The active area is passivated by a thin interfacial $\text{SiO}_2/\text{SiN}_x$ stack, whereas the oxide separating contact regions is a thicker field oxide. For implanted-junction variants, the active area received an additional shallow n-type (As or Sb) implantation before passivation. Reproduced based on the design reported in [3].

Capacitance-Voltage (C-V) measurements were performed using a Signatone S-1060R manual probe station connected to a Keithley 4200 Semiconductor Characterization System in parallel conductance mode at 1 kHz with an AC amplitude of 100 mV. Samples were briefly illuminated prior to each sweep to remove trapped charge effects, and all measurements were conducted in darkness.

The flatband voltage was determined from the C-V curves, and the effective charge density, Q_{eff} , was calculated from the flatband shift using the measured oxide capacitance. The metal-semiconductor work function difference was calculated individually for each sample based on the substrate doping concentration extracted from the depletion region ($1/C^2-V$) slope. Series resistance correction was evaluated and found to have negligible impact at 1 kHz; therefore, no correction was applied to the presented data.

The injection-dependent effective minority carrier lifetime was measured at 25 °C using Sinton WCT-120 systems (WCT-120 and WCT-120TS) operated in transient photoconductance decay (PCD) mode. All reported lifetime values correspond to an excess carrier concentration of $\Delta n = 1 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. Agreement between the two instruments was verified at this injection level. The surface saturation current density, J_{0s} , was extracted using the Kane-Swanson slope method [17].

Photoluminescence images were acquired using a BT Imaging LIS-R1 system with 808 nm excitation. The PL intensity was calibrated to effective minority carrier lifetime using a reference measurement obtained in the central region of each sample.

Implantation and annealing profile simulations were performed using Synopsys Advanced Technology Computer-Aided Design (TCAD) to guide the selection of screen oxide thickness, implant energies, doses, and annealing conditions for shallow junction formation. The simulated dopant distributions were subsequently compared with secondary ion mass spectrometry (SIMS) measurements performed by Eurofins EAG Laboratories on implanted and annealed wafers. Quantitative depth profiles of As and Sb were obtained, and depth calibration was performed by the service provider based on sputter crater measurements. The resulting profiles were used to determine dopant depth distribution and peak dopant concentration.

UV exposure was carried out using sources with nominal wavelengths of 300, 279, and 222 nm, with the corresponding normalized emission spectra presented in Figure S1. UV LEDs were used for irradiation at 300 and 279 nm (Thorlabs M300L4 and Laser Components LEUVA66H70HF00, respectively), while an excimer lamp was used for the irradiation at 222 nm (UVMedico UV222). Photodiode UV-exposure measurements were carried out at room temperature with an applied bias of 5 V. For wafer-level experiments, samples were positioned behind a 20 mm aperture, with a collimating tube placed between the UV source and the sample to define the illuminated area. For 222 nm exposure of the photodiodes, a mask with a circular aperture was attached directly to the device, resulting in an exposed area with a diameter of 8 mm. The irradiance at the photodiode surface was ca. 840 $\mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$ and was recorded before and after each measurement with a calibrated reference detector. During the measurement campaign, the 222 nm lamp intensity increased by ca. 0.5% per day. UV stability was evaluated as a function of accumulated radiant exposure (hereafter referred to as dose). For dose calculations, the irradiance during each individual measurement was approximated by linear interpolation between the recorded start and end values. Photocurrent was recorded at 10 s intervals.

Spectral responsivity measurements were performed before and after UV exposure on quadrants of selected photodiodes with a sensitive area of 11 mm \times 11 mm, using a spot diameter of 3.1 mm and with an applied reverse bias of 40 V. For each wavelength, the photocurrent of the sample was measured relative to that of a calibrated reference detector, and the responsivity change was evaluated from the ratio of the post-exposure and pre-exposure measurements. The reference-detector signal was corrected for temporal drift between the pre- and post-exposure measurement campaigns. One quadrant was left unexposed, while the remaining quadrants were exposed to different doses of 222 nm radiation. For wavelengths of 200 to 405 nm, the measurements were carried out using a xenon lamp and two 3-element reflection trap detectors with Hamamatsu S5227-1010 and S1337-1010 photodiodes, while for wavelengths of 395-1000 nm, a tungsten-halogen lamp and one 3-element reflection trap detector with Hamamatsu S6337 and one 6-element transmission trap detector with Hamamatsu S1337 photodiodes were used. A double-grating monochromator with order-sorting filters and a detector-positioning system was employed. The measurements were performed at 0° and 90° orientation to determine the spectral responsivity change for non-polarized radiation.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Preliminary investigation of induced junction photodiodes

Induced junction photodiodes previously fabricated using $\text{SiN}_x/\text{SiO}_2$ surface passivation were found to degrade under UV exposure at wavelengths of 279 nm and below [11]. To investigate the origin of this behaviour, MOS capacitors (MIS structures) were fabricated to quantify changes in dielectric fixed charge as a function of UV wavelength and dose. In parallel, symmetrically passivated double-side polished wafers were prepared to evaluate the impact of UV exposure on effective minority carrier lifetime.

The C-V characteristics measured after exposure to different UV wavelengths and doses are shown in Figure 2. For all investigated wavelengths (300, 279, and 222 nm), a clear flatband voltage shift is observed with increasing UV dose. The extracted effective charge density, Q_{eff} , decreases with increasing dose and approaches a saturation level beyond a characteristic exposure. The extracted fixed charge and the corresponding lifetime on symmetrically passivated samples are summarized in Table 1.

Both the effective charge and the carrier lifetime decrease rapidly upon initial UV exposure, followed by saturation at higher doses. For 222 and 279 nm Q_{eff} stabilizes at approximately $3 \times 10^{11} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, whereas for 300 nm, saturation is reached at a higher level of

Figure 2: Capacitance-Voltage characteristics at 1 kHz of MIS capacitors passivated with ca. 6 nm thermal SiO₂ and ca. 65 nm PECVD SiN_x after UV exposure at the indicated doses for (a) 300 nm, (b) 279 nm, (c) 222 nm.

Table 1: Evolution of effective fixed charge density Q_{eff} and average effective carrier lifetime (at an excess carrier concentration of $1 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) following UV exposure with peak wavelengths at 222, 279, and 300 nm for the indicated doses. The unexposed sample is included as a reference. “NM” denotes not measured.

Peak Wavelength (nm)	Dose (J/cm ²)	Q_{eff} (cm ⁻²)	Average Lifetime (ms) at $1 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$
No exposure	0	$(2.5 \pm 0.3) \times 10^{12}$	12.9 ± 3.3
222	0.001	1.6×10^{12}	10.8
222	0.01	3.1×10^{11}	4.7
222	0.1	2.9×10^{11}	5.6
279	0.1	1.2×10^{12}	8.5
279	1	2.8×10^{11}	4.5
279	10	2.8×10^{11}	5.1
300	0.01	NM	8.5
300	1	1.4×10^{12}	NM
300	10	8.0×10^{11}	7.8
300	100	7.0×10^{11}	7.7

ca. $7 \times 10^{11} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. In previous photodiode measurements [11], less than 0.4% photocurrent degradation was observed under 300 nm exposure. Taken together with the present MIS results, this suggests that an effective charge level on the order of $7 \times 10^{11} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ remains sufficient to sustain the induced inversion layer. In contrast, the reduction to ca. $3 \times 10^{11} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ at shorter wavelengths is consistent with the induced junction no longer being sufficiently sustained, resulting in loss of photocurrent.

The observed saturation behaviour suggests that UV exposure results in filling of a finite density of electrically active trap states in the dielectric stack, thereby reducing the net positive fixed charge. That the saturation level differs between 300 nm and the shorter wavelengths suggests that additional UV-activated charging pathways, or a larger fraction of electrically active states, become accessible at photon energies corresponding to 279 nm (4.4 eV). The similar saturation level observed at 279 nm and 222 nm further suggests that the dominant processes affecting the net charge evolution are already active at 279 nm under the present exposure conditions. The results are in agreement with previous studies reporting carrier injection from Si into the dielectric below certain wavelengths [10], [18], [19].

These results suggest that improved UV stability of induced-junction-based photodiodes may be achieved either by maintaining sufficient net positive dielectric charge after UV exposure or by reducing the density of UV-active electrically active states. In the

present study, these ideas are addressed indirectly through junction engineering and oxide process modifications.

3.2 Development of shallow As and Sb doping profiles

To reduce reliance on dielectric-induced inversion while maintaining efficient short-wavelength carrier collection, shallow n-type junctions were formed by ion implantation. Compared with phosphorus, heavier dopants such as As and Sb exhibit reduced projected range at a given implant energy and lower diffusivity during annealing, making them attractive candidates for realizing shallow profiles [20].

A range of implant energies and doses for both As and Sb was first screened using implantation profile simulations, and the most promising conditions were then evaluated experimentally using furnace activation anneals (Table S1). Simulated profiles showed reasonable agreement with subsequent SIMS measurements (Figure S2 and Figure S3). To maintain a shallow junction while limiting implantation-induced damage in silicon, the implant energies were chosen such that the concentration peak remained within the screen oxide and only the tail of the distribution extended into the silicon. The primary design target was to obtain peak dopant concentrations 10^{19} – 10^{20} cm^{-3} in silicon, while keeping the dopant distribution as close to the surface as possible and limiting concentrations to a range compatible with electrical activation [21].

Because spreading resistance profiling (SRP) proved insufficiently reproducible for these very shallow junctions, the implant development relied on a combination of SIMS depth profiling, sheet resistance measurements, and injection-dependent lifetime/ J_{0s} extraction. Representative SIMS profiles for As implants (25 keV, varying dose) and Sb implants (varying energy and dose) after a 1 min, 900 °C activation anneal are shown in Figure 3. As expected, increasing implant dose primarily increased the near-surface concentration while maintaining a similar depth distribution, whereas Sb profiles showed a strong dependence on implant energy, with 40 keV producing a more pronounced near-surface peak compared with 30 keV at comparable dose.

Electrical passivation quality differed markedly between Sb implant energies. Wafers implanted with Sb at 40 keV exhibited significantly poorer surface passivation than those implanted at 30 keV, consistent with a higher near-surface defect density and/or incomplete electrical activation associated with the higher peak concentration. This is reflected in the injection-dependent lifetime behaviour and extracted surface saturation current density, where the 40 keV condition yielded substantially higher J_{0s} than the 30 keV condition (Figure 4). The extracted J_{0s} of ca. 110 fA/cm^2 for 30 keV wafer is also about an order of magnitude higher than for

Figure 3: SIMS profiles of silicon wafers with 30 nm screening oxide and implanted following (a) As at 25 keV for the indicated doses and (b) Sb implantation at the indicated doses and energies. The wafers were annealed for 1 min at 900 °C.

Figure 4: Photoconductance decay measurements on wafers implanted on each side with a dose of 1×10^{15} Sb/cm² at 30 and 40 keV and symmetrically passivated with ca. 4 nm of SiO₂ and 65 nm SiN_x before UV exposure. Each wafer was measured at 5 different locations across the wafer.

induced junction diodes. Assuming that the effective dielectric charge is of similar order to that in the induced-junction reference structures, the increased J_{0s} is consistent with increased interface-related recombination (e.g., higher D_{it} and/or implant-induced near-surface defects).

Based on these observations, selected Sb implant conditions (dose 1×10^{15} cm⁻² at 30 and 40 keV) were carried forward for UV exposure studies on symmetrically passivated wafers. After double-sided implantation and activation (1 min at 900 °C), the screen oxide was thinned to approximately 4 nm and a ca. 65 nm PECVD SiN_x layer was deposited on both sides. The wafers were then diced into 4×4 cm² samples for controlled UV exposure.

To evaluate spatial non-uniformities and localized degradation, photoluminescence images were acquired before and after spot exposures under the conditions outlined in Figure 5(a). Figures 5(b) and 5(c) show the photoluminescence images for the 40 keV and 30 keV Sb implants. A reduction in effective lifetime was observed in exposed regions for all tested implantation conditions, including at 300 nm. Compared with induced-junction samples exposed to the same doses, the implanted samples exhibited a larger relative

Figure 5: (a) Schematic overview of the individual sample pieces and their corresponding UV exposure conditions. (b,c) Photoluminescence images acquired before (top) and after (bottom) UV exposure for wafers implanted with Sb at a dose of 1×10^{15} Sb/cm² with implant energy of 40 keV (b) and 30 keV (c). The colour bar shows the effective minority carrier lifetime in μ s.

lifetime reduction at 300 nm, suggesting that UV exposure produces a stronger increase in surface-related recombination in these structures. Possible contributors include a higher density of electrically active defects in the interfacial oxide after implantation and oxide thinning, changes in the surface potential that modify carrier recombination near the interface, and/or greater UV-induced defect formation at the Si/SiO₂ interface. However, as lifetime reduction alone does not directly determine UV photodiode performance, photocurrent stability measurements are therefore required to assess whether shallow implantation improves UV stability.

3.3 UV stability of fabricated photodiodes with and without external doping

A batch of photodiodes was fabricated with multiple variations in dielectric stack and junction design (summarized in Table S2). The dielectric stack differed somewhat from the MIS and lifetime test structures discussed in Section 4.1; the latter were used primarily to identify general UV-induced trends in dielectric charge and passivation behaviour. UV stability was evaluated by monitoring photocurrent during 222 nm exposure and reporting the normalized photocurrent as a function of accumulated dose.

3.3.1 Induced Junction

A subset of the fabricated photodiodes was prepared as induced-junction devices, with only minor modifications relative to the previously reported SiO₂/SiN_x structures [3]. Two variations were evaluated: (i) increasing the interfacial oxide thickness from 6.5 to 15 nm, and (ii) replacing PECVD SiN_x with a thicker LPCVD SiN_x. The normalized photocurrent as a function of applied dose at 222 nm of the fabricated devices is presented in Figure 6. The two induced-junction devices with 100 nm PECVD SiN_x exhibited an initial photocurrent of approximately 30 μA under the applied measurement conditions, while it was approximately 23 μA for the one with 130 nm LPCVD SiN_x, with the difference likely being due to differences in reflection and absorption. Upon 222 nm exposure, the photocurrent decreased rapidly by 25–30% within the first seconds of exposure for all samples, corresponding to a dose of 0.1 J/cm², followed by a slower degradation toward a quasi-stable level of ca. 50% within approximately two hours.

Within the investigated range, increasing the interfacial oxide thickness to 15 nm did not produce a clear change in the 222 nm degradation behaviour.

Figure 6: Normalized photocurrent vs. dose at 222 nm for induced junction photodiodes with varying SiO₂ thickness, SiN_x thickness, and SiN_x deposition method (note log scale).

For the devices employing a 6.5 nm interfacial SiO₂ layer and a ca. 95 nm PECVD SiN_x cap, continued exposure led to a delayed collapse in photocurrent after ca. 10 hours, consistent with earlier observations in similar structures [11]. The device with a thicker LPCVD SiN_x layer did not exhibit a comparable late-stage collapse within the measured dose range (up to 50 J/cm²), but more data would be required to determine whether this is representative behaviour.

Overall, the three induced-junction photodiodes exhibited similar response to UV exposure, indicating that, within the limited set of variations investigated here, these changes did not substantially improve UV stability. This points to processes associated with the common Si/SiO₂ interfacial region as a likely major contributor to the degradation. The observed behaviour is also qualitatively consistent with the results in Section 4.1, where the degradation was associated with a saturating reduction in effective net dielectric charge inferred from C–V measurements. UV-induced Si–H bond breaking in SiN_x-based passivation has been reported previously [9], [12], and may contribute here as well. However, the present results do not allow a unique separation of all microscopic degradation pathways. The charge-evolution picture nevertheless provides a simple and consistent framework for understanding the observed photocurrent loss.

3.3.2 Implanted Junction

Photodiodes incorporating shallow implanted junctions (Sb or As) were fabricated using a 15 nm SiO₂/26 nm PECVD SiN_x stack. The normalized photocurrent as a function of applied dose at 222 nm of the fabricated devices is presented in Figure 7a (Sb) and 7b (As). These devices exhibited a slightly lower initial photocurrent (ca. 25 μA) than the induced-junction photodiodes. Because the initial photocurrent was similar across all implanted variants, the difference is most plausibly explained by systematic optical effects (e.g., reflectance differences associated with dielectric thickness), rather than junction- or defect-related electrical losses. Similar to the induced-junction devices, and as expected based on the lifetime measurements, the implanted-junction photodiodes showed an immediate response during the first seconds of exposure, but the magnitude of the initial drop was <12%, as opposed to 25% to 30% for the induced junction devices.

In contrast to induced-junction photodiodes, both Sb- and As-implanted devices stabilized at significantly higher normalized photocurrent, approaching 80–85% of the initial value (corresponding to ca. 20 μA under the present measurement conditions). Sb-implanted photodiodes stabilized after receiving a dose of ca. 75 J/cm², whereas As-implanted devices did not stabilize completely within the longest exposure time corresponding to a dose of 125 J/cm². After exposure, all the externally implanted photodiodes

Figure 7: Normalized photocurrent vs. dose at 222 nm for photodiodes passivated with 15 nm SiO₂ and 26 nm PECVD SiN_x and doped with (a) Sb, and (b) As.

delivered higher photocurrent than the induced-junction photodiodes under prolonged 222 nm exposure, despite their slightly lower initial photocurrent.

Overall, these results demonstrate that introducing a shallow implanted junction substantially improves UV stability at 222 nm. The improvement is consistent with reduced device dependence on dielectric-induced inversion, allowing carrier collection to be maintained more effectively as the dielectric charge state evolves during exposure.

3.4 Repairing oxide after implant

The preliminary results in Section 4.1 suggest that UV exposure reduces the effective positive charge in the dielectric stack through a saturating process, consistent with filling of a finite population of electrically active oxide/interface traps. For photodiodes incorporating shallow implants, additional implantation-related damage in the screen oxide and at the Si/SiO₂ interface may further increase interface recombination and cause or accelerate UV-induced performance loss. These considerations motivate an approach in which the screen oxide is removed after activation and replaced by a regrown thermal oxide, thereby replacing the implantation-affected interfacial oxide with newly grown thermal oxide and potentially reducing the density of UV-accessible traps and/or interface states. The downside of this approach is that thermal regrowth of the oxide requires a high-temperature process that drives the dopants deeper into the silicon, causing the photogenerated carriers to require higher lifetime to reach the depletion region. A highly doped region near the surface is also often considered a “dead” layer with respect to charge collection. However, since UV photons are absorbed within the first few nanometres of silicon, it is not possible to make the doping layer so shallow that the UV photons do not interact with it. Consequently, it is more important to ensure that the carrier lifetime in the highly doped region remains sufficient for charge collection.

To evaluate the effect of regrowing the interfacial oxide, As-implanted photodiodes (25 keV, 1×10^{16} cm⁻²) were fabricated using two oxide process sequences following activation and prior to 26 nm PECVD SiN_x deposition: (i) retaining ca. 15 nm of the original screen oxide by thinning the oxide, and (ii) stripping the screen oxide and regrowing a ca. 23 nm thermal SiO₂ layer. The regrown oxide thickness differed from the retained oxide due to the higher thermal oxidation rate of the highly doped surface making it hard to predict the final oxide thickness. As discussed in the previous section, variations in oxide thickness within this general range did not produce a clear trend in the induced-junction devices studied here, suggesting that the improved behaviour of the regrown-oxide device is unlikely to arise from oxide thickness alone.

The normalized photocurrent during 222 nm exposure for the two oxide process sequences is shown in Figure 8a, while the corresponding SIMS profiles after removal of the dielectric stack are shown in Figure 8b. The device fabricated with regrown oxide exhibited a slightly lower initial photocurrent (ca. 22 μA) than the retained-oxide device (ca. 25 μA), which is consistent with increased optical losses expected from the thicker oxide and associated changes in reflectance. However, the regrown-oxide device showed substantially improved stability under prolonged 222 nm exposure. After approximately six days of exposure (corresponding to ca. 500 J/cm²), the photocurrent remained close to its initial level (ca. 22 μA) and exceeded the stabilized photocurrent of the retained-oxide device (ca. 20 μA) despite the lower starting value. Because of the strong stability observed in the regrown-oxide sample, the measurement was extended in a separate follow-up run to higher accumulated dose, as indicated in Figure 8a.

Figure 8: (a) Normalized photocurrent as a function of accumulated dose at 222 nm for As-implanted samples (25 keV , $1 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-2}$) fabricated with either retained 15 nm screen oxide (red) or stripped and regrown 23 nm thermal SiO_2 prior to 26 nm SiN_x deposition (blue). The inset shows the initial 150 J/cm^2 on a linear dose scale. For the regrown-oxide sample, the data above approximately 72 J/cm^2 were acquired in a separate follow-up measurement and aligned to the end of the initial run for plotting. (b) SIMS profiles of total As in Si for the corresponding devices after stripping the dielectric stack.

A minor initial increase in photocurrent (ca. 2%) was observed during the early stage of exposure before a gradual decrease for the photodiode with regrown oxide. The irradiance measured by the reference detector showed an approximately 0.5% increase after the initial dose of 72 J/cm^2 and a 3% increase at the end of the six-day measurement, indicating that the initial rise in photocurrent might be partly associated with increasing irradiance over time, but cannot be explained by irradiance variation alone. This interpretation is also consistent with spectral responsivity measurements performed on different photodiodes from the same wafer before and after exposure to various doses at 222 nm (Figure S4), which showed a ca. 2% increase in responsivity at 222 nm for a dose of 100 J/cm^2 . The origin of this increase remains unclear, but a similar responsivity peak near 222 nm was also observed for the diode with retained screen oxide. Since these shortest wavelengths are most sensitive to the dielectric stack and the near-surface collection conditions, this common feature may reflect a UV-induced modification of the surface region, for example through changes in optical losses and/or carrier collection very close to the surface. The much larger and broader spectral change observed for the retained-oxide sample indicates that additional degradation mechanisms are present in that structure. Finally, it should be noted that the apparent late-stage decrease in the logarithmic-dose representation is partly influenced by axis compression; when plotted on a linear dose scale (inset in Figure 8a), the response is consistent with stabilization rather than accelerating degradation.

SIMS measurements (Figure 8b) confirmed that the strip-and-regrow process altered the near-surface dopant distribution relative to the retained-screen-oxide sample. The regrown-oxide sample exhibited a lower measured near-surface concentration and a broader profile extending deeper into the silicon, consistent with oxidation-driven consumption of the most heavily doped surface region and additional thermal redistribution of As during reoxidation. Despite the broader near-surface dopant distribution in the regrown-oxide sample, the devices showed markedly improved UV stability. This indicates that the improvement cannot be understood simply in terms of making the junction as shallow and sharply peaked as possible and instead points to an important role of the oxide/interface condition after implantation.

440

441

442

443

444

445

446

447

448

449

450

451

452

453

454

455

456

457

458

459

460

461

462

463

464

465

466

467

468

469

470

471

472

473

474

475

476

477

478

4. Conclusion

In this work, the UV stability of SiO₂/SiN_x-passivated silicon photodiodes was investigated with particular focus on degradation at 222 nm and methods for improving stability through shallow junction implantation and oxide processing.

Measurements on induced-junction structures showed that UV exposure reduces the effective positive charge in the dielectric stack and lowers the effective carrier lifetime. For exposure at 222 and 279 nm, the effective charge saturated at approximately $3 \times 10^{11} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, whereas exposure at 300 nm saturated at a higher level of approximately $7 \times 10^{11} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. Comparison with previous photocurrent measurements indicates that the higher saturation level at 300 nm remains sufficient to sustain the induced inversion layer, while the lower saturation level reached at 222 and 279 nm is associated with a collapse of the induced junction. The saturation behaviour is consistent with filling of a finite population of electrically active trap states in the dielectric stack.

To reduce device dependence on dielectric-induced inversion, shallow As- and Sb-implanted junctions were developed. SIMS, sheet resistance, and lifetime/ J_{0s} analysis showed that shallow implanted junctions could be achieved while still maintaining reasonably low recombination losses.

Despite the higher recombination associated with implantation, externally implanted photodiodes exhibited substantially improved UV stability at 222 nm compared with induced-junction photodiodes. Induced-junction devices exhibited an immediate photocurrent drop of 25–30%, followed by degradation toward approximately 50% of the initial value. Some devices collapsed completely upon prolonged exposure. In contrast, implanted-junction devices stabilized at around 80–85% of their initial photocurrent up to the highest tested dose of 200 J/cm². These results indicate that shallow implanted junctions can preserve carrier collection even as the dielectric charge evolves during UV exposure.

Finally, replacing the retained screen oxide with a stripped and regrown thermal oxide provided a further substantial improvement in UV stability. The regrown-oxide devices maintained nearly unchanged photocurrent during prolonged 222 nm exposure up to approximately 500 J/cm², clearly outperforming devices fabricated with retained screen oxide. This result strongly suggests that post-implantation oxide/interface quality is an important factor governing UV stability, likely through its influence on electrically active oxide/interface trap states and interface-related recombination.

Overall, the results are most consistent with UV degradation in SiO₂/SiN_x-based induced-junction photodiodes at 222 nm being driven largely by reduction of effective dielectric charge and the resulting weakening or loss of surface inversion, while in implanted-junction devices the remaining degradation appears to be influenced more strongly by surface and interface recombination than by complete loss of junction functionality. Shallow implanted junctions, especially when combined with regrown thermal oxide, provide a promising route toward significantly improved UV-stable silicon photodiodes for precision radiometric applications.

Funding: The project 22IEM06 S CALe Up has received funding from the European Partnership on Metrology (ID: 10.13039/100019599), co-financed from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and by the Participating States.

Author Contributions: Conceptualization, O.K. and J.G.; Methodology, M.N.G., O.K., F.E., S.H., T.P., S.K., Ø.N., M.P., E.I., and L.W.; Validation, F.E., S.K., S.H., T.P., M.N.G., and M.P.; Formal analysis, M.N.G. and O.K.; Investigation, M.N.G., O.K., Ø.N., F.E., and S.H.;

Resources, M.N.G., O.K., M.P., Ø.N., F.E., S.K., S.H., and L.W.; Data curation, M.N.G., F.E., M.P., Ø.N., and S.H.; Writing-original draft preparation, M.N.G.; Writing-review and editing, O.K., E.I., J.G., Ø.N., L.W., and T.P.; Visualization, M.N.G. and Ø.N.; Supervision, O.K., J.G., S.K., E.I., and L.W.; Project administration, J.G. and O.K.; Funding acquisition, J.G., O.K., and E.I. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Data Availability Statement: The data supporting this study are available upon reasonable request.

Acknowledgments: The authors thank Leny Nazareno for wafer processing in the cleanroom and Eivind Bardalen for photodiode packaging.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest

References

1. I. Müller *et al.*, 'Predictable quantum efficient detector: II. Characterization and confirmed responsivity', *Metrologia*, vol. 50, no. 4, p. 395, Jul. 2013, doi: 10.1088/0026-1394/50/4/395.
2. T. Dönsberg, M. Sildoja, F. Manoocheri, M. Merimaa, L. Petroff, and E. Ikonen, 'A primary standard of optical power based on induced-junction silicon photodiodes operated at room temperature', *Metrologia*, vol. 51, no. 3, p. 197, May 2014, doi: 10.1088/0026-1394/51/3/197.
3. O. Koybasi *et al.*, 'High Performance Predictable Quantum Efficient Detector Based on Induced-Junction Photodiodes Passivated with SiO₂/SiNx', *Sensors*, vol. 21, no. 23, p. 7807, Nov. 2021, doi: 10.3390/s21237807.
4. L. Werner *et al.*, 'Quantum yield in induced-junction silicon photodiodes at wavelengths around 400 nm', *Metrologia*, vol. 61, no. 3, p. 035002, Apr. 2024, doi: 10.1088/1681-7575/ad310d.
5. M. Sildoja *et al.*, 'Predictable quantum efficient detector: I. Photodiodes and predicted responsivity', *Metrologia*, vol. 50, no. 4, p. 385, Jul. 2013, doi: 10.1088/0026-1394/50/4/385.
6. T. E. Hansen, 'Silicon UV-Photodiodes Using Natural Inversion Layers', *Physica Scripta*, vol. 18, no. 6, p. 471, Dec. 1978, doi: 10.1088/0031-8949/18/6/025.
7. W. K. Schubert, C. H. Seager, and K. L. Brower, 'Creation of Interface States at the Silicon/Silicon Dioxide Interface by UV Light Without Hole Trapping', *MRS Online Proceedings Library*, vol. 148, no. 1, pp. 415–420, Dec. 1989, doi: 10.1557/PROC-148-415.
8. L. E. Black and K. R. McIntosh, 'Defect Generation at Charge-Passivated Si-SiO₂ Interfaces by Ultraviolet Light', *IEEE Transactions on Electron Devices*, vol. 57, no. 8, pp. 1996–2004, Aug. 2010, doi: 10.1109/TED.2010.2051199.
9. R. Witteck *et al.*, 'UV radiation hardness of photovoltaic modules featuring crystalline Si solar cells with AlO_x/p+-type Si and SiNy/n+-type Si interfaces', *physica status solidi (RRL) – Rapid Research Letters*, vol. 11, no. 8, p. 1700178, Aug. 2017, doi: 10.1002/pssr.201700178.
10. A. Sinha *et al.*, 'UV-induced degradation of high-efficiency silicon PV modules with different cell architectures', *Progress in Photovoltaics*, vol. 31, no. 1, pp. 36–51, Jan. 2023, doi: 10.1002/pip.3606.
11. A. Kilpeläinen *et al.*, 'Degradation characterization of induced junction photodiodes under ultraviolet irradiation', *Metrologia*, vol. 63, no. 2, p. 025006, Apr. 2026, doi: 10.1088/1681-7575/ae4c8f.
12. R. Witteck *et al.*, 'UV-stable surface passivation for crystalline silicon cells in solar modules with UV light transmitting encapsulation materials', in *2019 IEEE 46th Photovoltaic Specialists Conference (PVSC)*, Jun. 2019, pp. 2238–2242. doi: 10.1109/PVSC40753.2019.8980612.
13. T. C. Kho *et al.*, 'Exceptional silicon surface passivation by an ONO dielectric stack', *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells*, vol. 189, pp. 245–253, Jan. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.solmat.2018.05.061.
14. S. W. Glunz and F. Feldmann, 'SiO₂ surface passivation layers – a key technology for silicon solar cells', *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells*, vol. 185, pp. 260–269, Oct. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.solmat.2018.04.029.

15. R. S. Bonilla, I. Al-Dhahir, M. Yu, P. Hamer, and P. P. Altermatt, 'Charge fluctuations at the Si-SiO₂ interface and its effect on surface recombination in solar cells', *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells*, vol. 215, p. 110649, Sep. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.solmat.2020.110649. 575
576
577
16. T. S. Stokkan, H. Haug, C. K. Tang, E. S. Marstein, and J. Gran, 'Enhanced surface passivation of predictable quantum efficient detectors by silicon nitride and silicon oxynitride/silicon nitride stack', *Journal of Applied Physics*, vol. 124, no. 21, p. 214502, Dec. 2018, doi: 10.1063/1.5054696. 578
579
580
17. D. E. Kane and R. M. Swanson, 'Measurement of the emitter saturation current by a contactless photoconductivity decay method', in *18th IEEE photovoltaic specialists conference, Las Vegas, IEEE, New York, 1985*, pp. 578–583. 581
582
18. D. A. Buchanan, A. D. Marwick, D. J. DiMaria, and L. Dori, 'Hot-electron-induced hydrogen redistribution and defect generation in metal-oxide-semiconductor capacitors', *Journal of Applied Physics*, vol. 76, no. 6, pp. 3595–3608, Sep. 1994, doi: 10.1063/1.357420. 583
584
585
19. P. E. Gruenbaum, R. A. Sinton, and R. M. Swanson, 'Stability problems in point contact solar cells', in *Conference Record of the Twentieth IEEE Photovoltaic Specialists Conference*, Sep. 1988, pp. 423–428 vol.1. doi: 10.1109/PVSC.1988.105736. 586
587
20. S. Koffel *et al.*, 'Precipitation of Antimony Implanted into Silicon', *ECS Transactions*, vol. 41, no. 34, p. 9, May 2012, doi: 10.1149/1.3697457. 588
589
21. K. Shibahara, 'Ultra-Shallow Junction Formation with Antimony Implantation', *IEICE Transactions on Electronics*, vol. E85-C, no. 5, pp. 1091–1097, May 2002. 590
591
592

Disclaimer/Publisher's Note: The statements, opinions and data contained in all publications are solely those of the individual author(s) and contributor(s) and not of MDPI and/or the editor(s). MDPI and/or the editor(s) disclaim responsibility for any injury to people or property resulting from any ideas, methods, instructions or products referred to in the content. 593
594
595

Supplementary Material

for “Improving UV Stability of SiO₂/SiN_x-Passivated Silicon Photodiodes Through Shallow Junction Implantation and Oxide Regrowth”

Figure S1: Normalized emission spectra of the UV sources used for exposure experiments with peak wavelengths of 222, 279, and 301 nm. The source with a peak at 301 nm has a nominal wavelength of 300 nm and is referred to as having a peak wavelength of 300 nm in the main paper.

Table S1: Implantation and annealing parameters evaluated for obtaining shallow n⁺ profiles using furnace activation. These data summarize implant and annealing conditions evaluated by 4-point probe and SIMS during junction optimization. Conditions for UV stability testing were selected based on evaluation of the resulting SIMS profiles and the measured sheet resistivity.

Implant species	Energy (keV)	Dose (at/cm ²)	Annealing Temperature (°C)	Annealing Duration (min)	Sheet Resistance 4-point probe (Ω/sq)
As	25	2×10 ¹⁴	900	1	3 692
As	25	5×10 ¹⁴	900	1	2 260
As	25	1×10 ¹⁵	900	1	1 544
As	25	1×10 ¹⁶	900	1	222
As	35	1×10 ¹⁵	900	1	556
As	35	1×10 ¹⁶	900	1	182
Sb	30	1×10 ¹⁴	900	1	11 650
Sb	30	1×10 ¹⁵	900	1	2 630
Sb	40	1×10 ¹⁴	900	1	3 635
Sb	40	1×10 ¹⁵	900	1	867
Sb	55	2×10 ¹⁵	900	1	451
Sb	55	1×10 ¹⁶	900	1	708
Sb	30	1×10 ¹⁵	900	10	2 799
Sb	30	1×10 ¹⁵	900	60	3 040
Sb	40	1×10 ¹⁵	900	10	951
Sb	40	1×10 ¹⁵	900	60	1 022

Table S2: Overview of parameters used for the photodiode production. “NA” denotes “Not Applicable”. The listed SiN_x thicknesses correspond to the final thickness. The as-deposited layers were thicker, but their thickness was reduced during subsequent cleaning/process steps prior to completion of the devices.

Implantation	Implant Species	Screen Oxide thickness (nm)	Energy (keV)	Dose (at/cm ²)	Passivation Process
Beamline	Sb	30	30	1×10 ¹⁵	Anneal 900°C, 10 min, Leave ca. 15 nm screen oxide, 26 nm PECVD SiN _x
Beamline	Sb	30	40	1×10 ¹⁵	Anneal 900°C, 10 min, Leave ca. 15 nm screen oxide, 26 nm PECVD SiN _x
Beamline	As	30	25	6×10 ¹⁴	Anneal 900°C, 10 min, Leave ca. 15 nm screen oxide, 26 nm PECVD SiN _x
Beamline	As	30	25	1×10 ¹⁶	Anneal 900°C, 10 min, Leave ca. 15 nm screen oxide, 26 nm PECVD SiN _x
Beamline	As	30	25	1×10 ¹⁶	Strip and regrow 23 nm thermal SiO ₂ , 26 nm PECVD SiN _x
None	NA	NA	NA	NA	15 nm thermal SiO ₂ , 95 nm PECVD SiN _x
None	NA	NA	NA	NA	6.5 nm thermal SiO ₂ , 95 nm PECVD SiN _x
None	NA	NA	NA	NA	6.5 nm thermal SiO ₂ , 130 nm LPCVD Si ₃ N ₄

Figure S2: SIMS profiles for As-implanted wafers through a 30 nm screen oxide and 1 min furnace annealing. Dashed lines show the corresponding TCAD simulated profiles for total As.

Figure S3: SIMS profiles for wafers implanted with 1×10¹⁵ Sb/cm² through a 30 nm screen oxide and (a) with varying implant energy and 10 min furnace annealing, and (b) 30 keV implant energy and varying furnace annealing durations. Dashed lines show the corresponding TCAD simulated profiles for total Sb.

Figure S4: Spectral responsivity ratio $S_{\text{after}}/S_{\text{before}}$, for photodiodes with retained screen oxide (a) and regrown oxide (b) after exposure to the indicated 222 nm doses. The pre- and post-exposure spectral responsivity measurements were separated by approximately four months. Measurements were performed on photodiodes from the same wafer as the devices shown in Figure 8 of the main text. Two light sources were used to cover complementary wavelength ranges: open circles denote data acquired using a tungsten-halogen lamp (395-1005 nm), while filled circles denote data acquired using a xenon arc lamp (198-405 nm).